

Planar intramolecular charge transfer effects on meloxicam and piroxicam drugs with α - and β -cyclodextrins : Spectral and molecular modeling studies

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Abstract : Inclusion complexation of meloxicam and piroxicam with α -CD and β -CD were studied by UV-Visible, fluorescence, time resolved fluorescence and molecular modeling techniques. Dual emission noticed in the CD solutions recommended that the energy of the intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) state is lower than that of the locally excited state. The shorter wavelength band was originated from the locally excited state and the longer wavelength band was due to the planar intramolecular charge transfer (PICT) state emission. The ratio of the PICT emission to the normal emission marginally increased with β -CD concentration, while it was slightly increased upon addition of α -CD. The above behavior indicating the formation of different 1 : 1 drug : CD inclusion complexes. The size of the benzamido ring suggested that the orientation of the drug in the β -CD complex is different from that in the α -CD complex. PM3 calculations were also carried out to assign the encapsulation of the drug molecules.

Keywords : Meloxicam, piroxicam, cyclodextrin, inclusion complex, molecular modeling.

Introduction

The electron donor-acceptor π -conjugated (D- π -A) compounds have been used as many applications in material science range, such as nonlinear optical materials¹, electrogenerated chemiluminescence materials^{2,3}, fluorescence probes⁴ and dye-sensitized solar cells⁵. The photo-induced intramolecular charge-transfer (ICT) character of the excited state in the D- π -A compounds is key to their excellent optical and electronic properties⁶. Thus, characterization of the ICT state (e.g. electronic nature and molecular geometry) will give deep insight into the relationship between molecular structures and properties.

In 1961, Lippert *et al.*, discovered the dual fluorescence first in the 4-(*N,N*-dimethylamino) benzonitrile (DMABN) compound^{7,8}. They found it is due to the charge transfer from electron donor group to electron acceptor group. Lippert *et al.* named the dual fluorescence as intramolecular charge transfer (ICT). After that, several theoretical and experimental studies carried out to analyse the origin of ICT fluorescence⁷⁻¹⁵. However, even for DMABN, the structure of ICT state is still ambiguous^{9,12}. Several distinct models, especially for the twisted intramolecular charge transfer (TICT)^{10,11} and

planar intramolecular charge transfer (PICT)^{12,13}, have been proposed to explain the formation and the final structure of the ICT state. Although some direct experimental proofs of excited-state structures have been obtained by picosecond X-ray diffraction¹⁶, transient infrared spectroscopy¹⁷ and laser-induced fluorescence excitation spectroscopy^{18,19} technologies, it's also difficult to determine the ICT excited-state geometry for most cases. In recent years, experimental and theoretical calculations are employed to interpret the properties of various donor-acceptor substituted systems^{20,21}. It is found that the theoretical analysis is an appropriate technique to get insight into the characters of the ground and excited states, as well as the mechanism of the ICT processes¹⁰⁻¹⁵.

In this study, we report the combined experimental and theoretical studies on the ICT processes in meloxicam and piroxicam π -conjugated donor-acceptor drug molecules. The hydroxy group fixed by the six member ring (benzothiazine) in both drugs makes the electron donor moiety more rigid and will decrease the complexity of structural changes in the discussion of the excited-state geometries below. The five or six membered heterocyclic ring (thiazolyl or pyridinyl) has employed as the con-

jugating units on designing novel push-pull structures, since hetero aromatic ring has lower delocalization energy than benzene, it can offer a more effective conjugation in donor-acceptor compounds²².

In our earlier studies, we have reported the ICT property of many drug molecules²³⁻³¹. Recently, we have studied many molecules where the proton donor groups are -NH₂, -OCH₃ and -OH but the proton acceptor groups are N=N, =N-, C=O, etc. In the present work, the electron acceptor group is the thiazolyl or pyridinyl moiety and donor group is hydroxyl group which is present in the benzothiazine moiety. Since the =N- or CO group is a better electron acceptor than -SO₂NH- it may facilitate the formation of the ICT state in the drug molecules

than sulphanilamides and hydroxyl benzaldehydes. It is interesting to analyze the changes produced in the spectral properties when these drugs form inclusion complexes. Herein, we have studied the inclusion complexes of meloxicam and piroxicam (Fig. 1) with α -CD and β -CD. The main aims of the present study are : (i) to compare the effect of the electron withdrawing meloxicam and piroxicam molecules on the ICT emission, and (ii) the inclusion complexes whether increase or decrease the LW emission. The results are obtained by the UV-Visible, steady state fluorescence, time resolved fluorescence measurement and molecular modeling methods.

Meloxicam (4-hydroxy-2-methyl-*N*-(5-methyl-2-thiazolyl)-2*H*-1,2-benzothiazine-3-carboxamide -1,1-diox-

Fig. 1. Chemical and PM3 optimized structures of (a, c) meloxicam and (b,d) piroxicam.

ide) is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) with analgesic and fever/pain reducer effects. It is a derivative of oxicam, closely related to piroxicam, and falls in the enolic acid group of NSAIDs^{32,33}. Meloxicam is also used in the veterinary field, most commonly in dogs and cats, but also sees off-label use in other animals such as cattle and exotics^{32,33}. It is also prescribed and licensed for other anti-inflammatory benefits including relief from both acute and chronic pain in dogs.

Piroxicam (4-hydroxy-2-methyl-*N*-(2-pyridinyl)-2*H*-1,2-benzothiazine-3-carboxamide-1,1-dioxide) is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) of the oxicam class used to relieve the symptoms of painful, inflammatory conditions like arthritis³⁴. It is used in the treatment of rheumatoid and osteoarthritis, primary dysmenorrhoea, postoperative pain; and act as an analgesic, especially where there is an inflammatory component³⁴.

Experimental

Materials :

Meloxicam, piroxicam, α -CD and β -CD were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich chemical company, USA and used without further purification. The purity of the compound was checked for similar fluorescence spectra when excited with different wavelengths. Triply distilled water was used for the preparation of aqueous solutions.

Preparation of CD solution :

The concentration of stock solution of the meloxicam and piroxicam drugs was 2×10^{-3} M. The stock solution (0.2 ml) was transferred into 10 ml volumetric flasks. To this, varying concentration of CD solution (1×10^{-3} to 1×10^{-2} M) was added. The mixed solution was diluted to 10 ml with triply distilled water and shaken thoroughly. The final concentration of meloxicam and piroxicam drugs in all the flasks was 4×10^{-5} M. The experiments were carried out at room temperature.

Instruments :

Absorption spectral measurements were carried out with a Shimadzu UV 1601 PC model UV-Visible spectrophotometer and steady-state fluorescence measurements were made by using a Shimadzu spectrofluorimeter model RF-5301. pH of the solution was measured in a Elico pH meter model LI-120. Fluorescence lifetime measurements were performed using a picoseconds laser and single pho-

ton counting setup from Jobin-Vyon IBH (Madras University, Chennai).

Molecular modeling studies :

Theoretical calculations were performed with Gaussian 09W package. The initial geometry of the meloxicam, piroxicam, α -CD and β -CD were constructed with the aid of Spartan 08 and then optimized by semiempirical PM3 method. CD was fully optimized by PM3 without any symmetry constraint³⁵. Glycosidic oxygen atoms of CD were placed onto the XY plane and their centre was defined as the centre of the coordination system. Primary hydroxyl groups were placed pointing toward the positive Z axis. Inclusion complex was constructed from the PM3 optimized CD and guest molecules. Longer dimension of the guest molecule was initially placed onto the Z axis. The position of the guest was determined by the Z coordinate of one selected atom of the guest. The inclusion process was simulated by putting the guest on one end of CD and then letting it pass through the CD cavities. Since the semiempirical PM3 method has been proved to be a powerful tool in the conformational study of CD inclusion complexes and has high computational efficiency³⁵, we selected semiempirical PM3 method to study the inclusion process of CDs with the drug molecules.

Results and discussion

Effects of α -CD and β -CD :

UV-Visible and emission spectral maxima, molar extinction coefficient, binding constant and Gibbs free energy change of meloxicam and piroxicam drugs in different concentrations of α -CD and β -CD are listed in Table S1 (Supplementary part). Absorption and fluorescence spectra of meloxicam and piroxicam drugs with various concentrations of α -CD and β -CD are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The inset in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 represent the changes in the absorption and fluorescence intensities of the drugs in the α -CD and β -CD solutions. Both meloxicam and piroxicam drugs consists of three absorption maxima (meloxicam \sim 359, 277, 229 nm and piroxicam \sim 336, 285, 251 nm). This may be due to the presence of different heterocyclic ring in the drug molecules. The absorption spectrum of meloxicam and piroxicam divided into three regions, namely : (i) longer wavelength (LW) absorption bands comprises the region at \sim 359 nm for meloxicam and 356 nm for piroxicam, (ii) middle wave-

Fig. 2. Absorbance and fluorescence spectra of meloxicam in different α -CD and β -CD concentrations (M): (1) 0, (2) 0.001, (3) 0.002, (4) 0.004, (5) 0.006, (6) 0.008, (7) 0.01. Insert: Absorbance and fluorescence intensity vs CD concentrations.

length (MW) band is around 277 nm for meloxicam and 285 nm for piroxicam, and (iii) shorter wavelength (SW) absorption band is at 229 nm for meloxicam 251 nm for piroxicam drug. The above results show that meloxicam and piroxicam having different type of absorption maxima. The MW band is ascribed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of the benzenoid system of the drug molecules, whereas the LW band can be attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition within the heterocyclic moiety (intramolecular hydrogen bonding, IHB ring) of the drug molecules. The location of LW band, relative to the MW can be ascribed due to the formation of IHB between carbonyl and -OH groups.

With increasing the α -CD and β -CD concentrations, no significant spectral shift observed in all the bands of the drugs. Upon increasing the CD concentrations, absorbance was slightly decreased in the meloxicam : CD solution whereas increased in the piroxicam : CD solution. The absorbance change in the meloxicam and piroxicam drugs with varying concentrations of the CDs suggests that both drugs are transferred more polar aque-

ous environment to non-polar CD cavities²³⁻³¹. The different absorbance changes indicates that different types of drug : CD inclusion complexes formed²³⁻³¹. A clear isosbestic point observed in the absorption spectra indicates that both drugs form 1 : 1 inclusion complexes with α -CD and β -CD.

Figs. 2 and 3 record the emission spectra of meloxicam and piroxicam drugs (excitation at 360 nm) with various α -CD and β -CD concentrations. Figs. 2 and 3 reflect a remarkable change in the emission properties of shorter wavelength (SW) and planar intramolecular charge transfer (PICT) states upon complexation. In absence of CD, the typical dual fluorescence of PICT can be noticed even though the normal emission intensities around 413 nm and the PICT around 475 nm is extremely low. The weak PICT emission has been most probably ascribed to the stabilization of the polar PICT state by dipole-dipole interaction with water and subsequent fast non-radiative transition to the ground and/or low-lying triplet state³⁶. Compared to β -CD, both normal and PICT emissions

Fig. 3. Absorbance and fluorescence spectra of piroxicam in different α -CD and β -CD concentrations (M): (1) 0, (2) 0.001, (3) 0.002, (4) 0.004, (5) 0.006, (6) 0.008, (7) 0.01. Insert: Absorbance and fluorescence intensity vs CD concentrations.

were slightly increased in the α -CD, and the emission maxima remain relatively unchanged (Figs. 2 and 3). The fluorescence intensity ratio of the PICT band and the normal band I_a/I_b were slightly varied when the concentration of α -CD increases.

Upon addition of drug to the aqueous β -CD solution, the PICT emission band is rather strongly enhanced with little enhancement of the normal emission. The PICT emission intensity effectively increased in the β -CD, however, the changes of the normal emission with addition of both CDs were very small. In other words, as the concentration of α -CD increases, the I_a/I_b ratio slightly changed than that of β -CD solution. The different spectral changes in the drug solutions suggest that the structural geometry of the both drug : α -CD complexes are different from that of the drug : β -CD inclusion complexes.

The experimental studies suggest that this peculiar spectroscopic results could be related to a twisted in-

tramolecular charge transfer (TICT) process, the same mechanism used to explain the anomalous dual fluorescence of 4,4'-dimethylaminobenzonitrile (DMABN)³⁷. From an electronic point of examination, TICT states are accessible in multichromophoric systems possessing a weakly coupled electron donor (D) and electron acceptor (A). Two stable conformations are then obtained in the lowest excited state by twisting the D and A moieties, one with respect to the other. As mentioned earlier in both drugs, the acceptor and donor parts are the heterocyclic ring or CO group and the hydroxy group, respectively, whereas the twisting angle (θ) corresponds to a rotation around the C-N bond (Fig. 1). Indeed the originally reached locally excited (LE) state with planar conformation has only a weak CT character (large mesomeric interaction between D and A results in an incomplete charge separation) whereas in the twisted TICT conformation, a significantly larger electronic charge is transferred from D to A, since the mesomeric interaction is blocked (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Donor-acceptor (D-A) type chromophore may twist or flatten in its excited state to form a TICT (twisted intramolecular charge transfer) state or a PICT (planar intramolecular charge transfer) state. FC – Franck-Condon state.

In alternative to the TICT process, another interpretation of experimental data, based on the so-called planar ICT (PICT) model, rejects the necessity of a large-amplitude motion for the formation of a highly polar ICT state³⁸. Such hypothesis is based on the equilibration dynamics between the LE and ICT state which takes place on a picosecond scale, with rates increasing when larger alkyl groups substitute the amino moiety³⁹. The PICT model postulates an ICT structure with an increased double bond character between the D and A moieties (C–N bond in the drugs), resulting in a partial positive charge on the -OH group and a heterocyclic ring resonance structure. In a more general interpretation of the model, it is claimed that the vibronic coupling could play a non-negligible role and that a large (nearly perpendicular) twist is unnecessary to form the highly polar ICT state^{40,41}.

To have a more direct analysis, it is convenient to define a charge transfer (CT) parameter as $f_{CT} = \Delta_{qD} - \Delta_{qA}$, where Δ_{qi} is the charge difference in the donor or acceptor unit between ground and excited state. If the excitation really corresponds to a CT from donor to acceptor, then Δ_{qD} is large and positive and Δ_{qA} is also large in absolute value but negative. As a result, f_{CT} will be large and positive. The donor and acceptor groups are the -OH and the heterocyclic ring moieties, respectively. The results obtained for the selected functional, reported in Table S2, refer to the 0 and 90 degrees values of twisting angle of the drug molecules. For the planar structure, all functional groups give the same picture and they indicate that there is not a significant CT, whereas different behaviors are found for the twisted structure.

To summarize, from the present analysis it comes out that both meloxicam and piroxicam presents important differences with respect to typical TICT systems such as

DMABN. In TICT systems, LE and CT states are usually very close to each other in the S_0 structure and their relative stability strongly depends on the θ angle: a planar ($\theta = \theta^0$) rearrangement correspond to a more stable LE configuration, whereas the CT state is lower in energy at the twisted conformation ($\theta = 90^\circ$). In contrast, both meloxicam and piroxicam is characterized by only one electronic state along the twisting coordinate; this behavior better fits with the PICT picture. Therefore, the origin of the double band in the absorption and fluorescence spectra should have another origin and some insights can be given by vibronic couplings.

Emission decay measurements :

To examine the CD-induced ICT changes in the fluorescence spectra of the drugs, we measured the emission decay of the normal (413 nm) and PICT emission (475 nm) in aqueous solutions (pH ~ 7) containing different concentrations of α -CD and β -CD. Fig. S1 depicts the PICT emission decay profiles in the presence of α -CD and β -CD. This analysis together with the normal emission decays is listed in Table S1. The normal emission decay in the absence of CD exhibits a slight fast decay as a major decay component with a small contribution of slow decay component. This decay behavior indicated the existence of the two different normal emitting species which compete with the conformational relaxation times required for the PICT state. The decay time of the slow component is similar to that of PICT emission within experimental error. This indicates that the equilibrium between the locally excited (LE) state and the PICT state is achieved in water in a rather short period. However, due to the formation of the inclusion complexes, the equilibrium between the LE and PICT states is modified. The decay time of the fast component remains the same with increasing the α -CD concentration, and its relative quantum yield increased significantly in contrast to its major change in β -CD solution. The decay time of the slow component increases significantly from water to 0.01 M α -CD and β -CD concentration.

The decay time of the PICT emission was observed to be very short in aqueous solution and also influenced by the addition of CD. This behavior indicated the competing process between the conformational relaxation required for the PICT state and the fast decay process of the nor-

mal emission. Upon addition of α -CD, the PICT emission decay profile is weak tri-exponential decay without significant enhancement of the lifetime and the relative quantum yield. With on addition of β -CD one decay components in the PICT emission appeared, suggesting the formation of different drug : α -CD and drug : β -CD inclusion complexes. The relative fluorescence quantum yields and their lifetimes do not change with the α -CD concentration. This is also consistent with little enhancement of the PICT emission in the α -CD solution (Figs. 2 and 3). A rise time of the PICT emission, which is different from the fast decay time of the normal emission, was increased as β -CD concentration increased, whereas it was not observed upon addition of α -CD. This reflects that the PICT dynamics of the drug : β -CD inclusion complex is quite different from that of the drug : α -CD complex.

To interpret the present results, we focus on three key observations of the PICT dynamics as well as the steady-state emission properties, namely, (i) a fast and a slow relaxational process are involved in the formation of the PICT state in water; (ii) the dynamics of the fast process is independent of the α -CD addition to water, while the rate of the slow process shows a linear dependence on the β -CD concentration, and the fast process dominates in water and (iii) the relative quantum yield of the fast process decreases significantly upon addition of β -CD in contrast to little change in the presence of α -CD.

The quick life time of the normal emission corresponds to the rise of the PICT emission, and it is quicker than the diffusion-controlled reaction time. Hence we assumed that the fast process is due to the excitation of the ground-state complex between the drug and water through hydrogen bonding as observed for drug in water/dioxane mixed solvent⁴². Considering that the lifetime of the slow process increases upon addition of β -CD to water, this slow process probably reflects the existence of excited drug molecules without water molecules in its neighbor or proper arrangement of water molecules for PICT to occur. This slow relaxational process is mainly due to a long-range polarization interaction to further stabilize the PICT state. It is to be mentioned that these two processes are differently affected by different CDs; the relative quantum yield of the fast process decreases significantly, while that of the slow process increases upon addition of β -CD

in contrast to little change in the quantum yield in the presence of α -CD.

The CD dependent triexponential decay times of the normal emission lead us to conclude that both the forward and reverse PICT rates in the aqueous solution underwent a change in the presence of CD. The above results confirmed the formation of the PICT state more favorably in the β -CD solution than in the α -CD solution. The CD dependences of the PICT dynamics may be interpreted on the basis of different solvent-solute interactions induced by forming different patterns of the inclusion complexes.

Since the fast process is due to the excitation of the ground-state complex between drug and water through hydrogen bonding, the different CD dependences of the relative quantum yields of the fast and slow relaxational processes imply that the hydrogen-bonding interaction between the drug and water molecules in the presence of α -CD is different from that in the presence of β -CD. In other words, both the -OH and carbonyl groups can be hydrogen-bonded with water, but the orientations of those two groups can be different with regard to water molecule, by forming different patterns of CD inclusion complexes depending on the kind of CDs.

The differences in the patterns of the inclusion complexes could be explained in terms of differences in the internal diameters of the α -CD and β -CD cavities as well as the dimensions of the meloxicam and piroxicam. To determine the dimensions of meloxicam and piroxicam, the geometry of the drug molecules in the ground state were optimized by using the PM3 program. This calculation revealed that the diameters of the both drugs are about 12 Å, which is larger than that of α -CD and β -CD cavities (5.6 Å and 6.5 Å). Therefore, the heterocyclic rings of the drugs are entrapped in the α -CD or β -CD cavities with the -OH and the benzothiazine group exposed to the bulk aqueous phase. Since meloxicam and piroxicam have different orientations in the α -CD and β -CD, it is clear that the increase in the relative quantum yield of the fast component of the normal emission upon addition of β -CD is due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding (IHB) between the -OH and carbonyl groups. As long as the carbonyl group is exposed to water, the magnitude of the contribution of the fast relaxational process

to form the PICT state stays the same as observed in the α -CD inclusion complex. Due to the presence of SO_2 group in the *para* position to the -OH group, the benzothiazine ring becomes larger in size relative to the α -CD or β -CD cavity. This may be also responsible for the formation of different types of inclusion complexes in the CD solution, as demonstrated by the two decay components of PICT emission.

Naturally, two different types of inclusion complex formation between meloxicam/piroxicam and CDs are possible. One is with the benzothiazine ring captured and the other is heterocyclic ring (thiazolyl or pyridinyl) captured in the CD cavity. In α -CD, the heterocyclic ring encapsulation is on the average more favorable than benzothiazine ring because of the larger size of the benzothiazine ring (i.e. -OH and SO_2 groups does not fit well to the rim of α -CD). Since the diameter of the β -CD cavity is higher than that of α -CD, -CONH- locates in a less polar environment of the β -CD cavity. Supporting this, the PICT intensity of the drugs is little increased with α -CD concentration, whereas that of β -CD, which effectively increased^{43,44}. Further, the presence of an isosbestic point seems to the formation of the well-defined 1 : 1 complex.

Also we attempted to evaluate the stoichiometry and binding constant of the inclusion complexes by monitoring the I_a/I_b ratio and using the Benansi-Hildebrand equation⁴⁵. Figs. 5 and 6 shows a straight line from the plot of the reciprocal of $1/\Delta A$ or $1/(I - I_0)$ vs the reciprocal of the CD concentration indicating 1 : 1 stoichiometry in the inclusion complexes. From the slope and intercept, the formation constant was determined. From Table S1, one can see the binding constant for drug : β -CD is larger than that of the drug : α -CD complex, because the orientation of the drugs in the α -CD cavity is different. The K values in the Table S1 indicate that the drug : β -CD inclusion complex is more stable than the drug : α -CD, which can be explained by β -CD having the optimal size for its internal cavity (6.5 Å) to encapsulate the drug molecules.

The small binding constant implies that the heterocyclic ring (thiazolyl or pyridinyl) is more deeply embedded in the β -CD cavity than α -CD and the rotation of the benzothiazine ring for PICT would be inhibited. The in-

Fig. 5. Benesi-Hildebrand plot for the complexation of meloxicam and piroxicam with α -CD and β -CD. (a and b) Plot of $1/A-A_0$ vs $1/[CD]$.

Fig. 6. Benesi-Hildebrand plot for the complexation of meloxicam and piroxicam with α -CD and β -CD. (a and b) Plot of $1/I-I_0$ vs $1/[CD]$.

crease of rise time of the PICT emission with increasing β -CD concentration is consistent with this speculation. However, the fact that the ICT emission is greatly enhanced in β -CD solution suggests that the rotation of the benzothiazine ring is still feasible in the β -CD cavity. Considering that PICT emission was observed in solid polymer matrices and/or under high pressure⁴⁶ it can be concluded that the restriction or the increased viscosity in the CD cavity does not affect the formation of the PICT state itself. The enhancement of the PICT emission of β -CD solution should be due to the reduced polarity of the CD environment^{43,44}. In a less polar environment, the ICT state is destabilized, and hence the energy gap between the PICT state and the Franck-Condon state is increased. This is supported by the blue-shift in the PICT emission of both drug molecules upon complexation with β -CD (Table S1). The increase in the energy gap causes a decrease in the nonradiative transition from the PICT state so that the PICT emission is enhanced. Such an increase in the energy gap is attributable to the reduced dipole-dipole interaction of the PICT state in the CD cavity.

The difference in the binding constants is also responsible for the fact that the I_a/I_b ratio of meloxicam/piroxicam in high concentration β -CD solution is much higher than that of α -CD solution. In other words, heterocyclic ring (thiazolyl or pyridinyl) is more deeply entrapped in the non-polar β -CD cavity than α -CD. Hence, the enhancement of the PICT emission seems to reflect the situation that the benzothiazine ring is protruded in the highly polar aqueous phase where the torsional energy barrier of the amino group for the formation of the PICT state is negligible. As a result, at first glance the torsional energy barrier for the formation of the PICT state is expected to be increased, when considering only the increase of the rise time for the PICT emission. Therefore, it would result in a marked increase of the normal emission. However, the normal emission turned out to be little enhanced as compared with the dramatic enhancement of the PICT emission, indicating that the energy barrier is not affected by the entrapment of benzothiazine ring in the non-polar β -CD cavity. From this observation, it can be concluded that the energy barrier for the formation of the PICT state is governed not only by the torsion of the -CONH- group but also by the hydrogen

bonding between the -CO- and -OH groups. As long as the intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the -CO and -OH group is effective, the energy barrier for the PICT is not changed. As already discussed, the reverse PICT slows down when the -CONH- group is entrapped in the non-polar β -CD cavity. This should be another reason why the PICT emission is greatly enhanced in the β -CD complex in contrast to little change in the α -CD complex. In aqueous solution, the back-torsion of the twist conformer formed promptly upon the photo-induced charge separation is required for the thermal repopulation of the LE state for the rapid equilibrium between the two emitting species. However, in the restricted environment of the β -CD cavity the back-torsion of the -CONH- group is inhibited as demonstrated by observation of the slow rise time in β -CD.

As discussed above, the orientation of meloxicam/piroxicam in the β -CD cavity is different to that in the α -CD, and it is rather similar to that of the piroxicam/ β -CD inclusion complex. As a part of the meloxicam/piroxicam molecules are located in the non-polar α -CD cavity, the PICT emission is expected to be enhanced substantially with an increase in the α -CD concentration as in the case of the β -CD inclusion complex. On the contrary, it was only slightly increased, as shown in Figs. 2 and 3. From Table S1, it is clear that the rise time corresponding to the conformational relaxation was too short to be measured even in the high concentration of α -CD solution. In this case the torsional barrier for the PICT process is negligible, as in the case of the drug : β -CD inclusion complex.

However, the PICT emission is rather dramatically enhanced even though the free torsional motion of the -CONH- group is still feasible. Thus, an alternative explanation is possible based on the fact that meloxicam/piroxicam have the heterocyclic ring or -CONH- group in contrast to the nitrile group in DEABN as an electron-withdrawing group^{7,8}. In aqueous solution the strong hydrogen bonding would be formed between water and the carbonyl group so that the -CONH- group becomes coplanar with the benzothiazine ring. Consequently, this hydrogen bonding seems to make a migration of electron density from the OH group to the carbonyl group heterocyclic ring or more facile for the fractional charge separation between heterocyclic ring (thiazolyl or pyridinyl)

and benzothiazine rings. On the other hand, by entrapment of the carbonyl group in the β -CD cavity, the fractional charge separation is inhibited by the hindrance of the hydrogen bonding between water and the carbonyl group. The hindrance of the hydrogen bonding is again supported by the decrease in the relative quantum yield of the fast component of normal emission in the β -CD solution (Table S1). Therefore, the normal emission band is enhanced relative to the PICT emission as the β -CD concentration increases.

Molecular modeling :

Semiempirical quantum mechanical calculations were made in order to get information related to the structural characteristics and thermodynamic properties of the meloxicam/piroxicam inclusion complexes with α -CD and β -CD. Table 1 depicts the energetic feature, HOMO-LUMO energy and thermodynamic parameters of the isolated meloxicam/piroxicam and its inclusion complexes with CDs. Frequency analysis was performed on the structure of the complex with lowest energy which were obtained during the inclusion process. Minimum energy optimized structure of the inclusion complexes are shown

in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. The negative energy of meloxicam : CD and piroxicam : CD inclusion complexes indicate that these complexes are energetically favorable. To investigate the thermodynamics of the inclusion process, the binding energies (ΔE), Gibbs energy changes (ΔG), enthalpy changes (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS) for the most stable inclusion complexes were calculated and are summarized in Table 1. The binding energy (ΔE) of the isolated drug molecule and the inclusion complex suggested that stability of complex is high compared to isolated molecule. The negative values for the complexes are demonstrated that the inclusion processes of both drugs with CDs are thermodynamically favorable. The lowest values for complexation energy correspond to the most stable complex. Among the four complexes meloxicam : β -CD ($-23.38 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) is lowest followed by piroxicam : β -CD ($-14.01 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$), meloxicam : α -CD ($-13.33 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$), and piroxicam : α -CD ($-8.31 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$).

The difference in energy (ΔE) values are a reasonable measure of hydrogen bonding and the change in hydrogen bonding of the drugs are caused only by the hydro-

Table 1. Energies, thermodynamic characteristics and HOMO-LUMO calculations for MEX, PIR, α -CD, β -CD and its inclusion complexes calculated by the PM3 method

Properties	MEX	PIR	α -CD	β -CD	MEX/ α -CD	MEX/ β -CD	PIR/ α -CD	PIR/ β -CD
E^a	-57.93	-57.83	-1247.52	-1457.63	-1318.78	-1538.94	-1313.76	-1529.47
ΔE^b					-13.33	-23.38	-8.31	-14.01
H^a	-121.14	85.06	-676.73	-789.52	-809.56	-929.95	-588.97	-712.15
ΔH^a					-11.69	-19.28	2.33	-7.69
G^a	-89.07	120.69	-571.21	-667.55	-679.34	-789.19	-457.17	-599.77
ΔG^a					19.06	32.56	-7.02	-52.91
S^b	-0.107	0.153	-0.353	-0.409	-0.403	-0.472	0.442	0.511
ΔS^b					-0.058	-0.044	-0.064	-0.051
E_{HOMO} (eV)	-9.04	-9.01	-10.38	-10.35	-9.11	-8.94	-9.29	-8.90
E_{LUMO} (eV)	0.14	-1.24	1.26	1.23	0.01	0.14	-1.49	-1.25
$E_{\text{HOMO}}-E_{\text{LUMO}}$ (eV)	-9.19	-7.77	-11.64	-11.58	-9.11	-9.09	-7.80	-7.65
μ (eV)	-4.45	-5.12	-4.56	-4.56	-4.55	-4.40	-5.39	-5.07
η (eV)	4.59	3.88	5.82	5.79	4.56	4.54	3.90	3.82
S (eV)	0.22	3.38	0.17	0.17	0.22	0.22	3.72	3.36
ω (eV)	2.15	0.25	1.78	1.79	2.27	2.13	0.25	0.26
Dipole (D)	0.97	7.71	11.34	12.29	10.14	11.06	11.65	9.96
Zero-point energy ^a	113.31	164.95	634.47	740.56	750.09	863.79	801.39	906.75
Mullikan charges	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Unit : ^akcal mol⁻¹; ^bkcal/mol-Kelvin.

gen ion concentrations. The energy involved in such hydrogen bond interaction is responsible for the higher or lower binding energy compared to those of the substituted or unsubstituted molecules. The ΔE for these inclusion complexes indicated that the interactions of hydrogen atoms of the drugs with CDs are much stronger than those of the drugs confirming that the interactions are due to the hydrogen bonding. Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 also suggest that hydrogen bonding is present in the meloxicam : CD and piroxicam : CD and the above two drugs are partially included in the CD cavities.

The free energy for the isolated meloxicam drug is negative and piroxicam drug is positive whereas the inclusion complex meloxicam : β -CD ($32.56 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$),

meloxicam : α -CD ($19.06 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) are positive while piroxicam : β -CD ($-52.91 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) and piroxicam : α -CD ($-7.02 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) inclusion complexes are negative. The negative free energy change (ΔG) of the piroxicam inclusion complexes suggest that the inclusion proceeds spontaneously at 303 K. The high negative ΔG value for piroxicam : β -CD inclusion complex indicates that this inclusion process is more spontaneous than the other complexes.

The enthalpy of the isolated meloxicam drug is also negative and piroxicam drug is positive whereas the inclusion complex enthalpies are negative. The negative ΔH values indicate that the formation of inclusion complexes of the drugs are exothermic and mostly enthalpy-

Fig. 7. Upper and side views of PM3 optimized structures of (a) meloxicam : α -CD, (b) piroxicam : α -CD inclusion complex.

Fig. 8. Upper and side views of PM3 optimized structures of (a) meloxicam : β -CD, (b) piroxicam : β -CD inclusion complex.

driven ($\Delta H > \Delta S$). It should be noted that ΔH and ΔS values contain contributions from (i) release of water found in the CD cavities, (ii) partial destruction of hydration shells of the reagents, (iii) non-covalent interactions and (iv) hydration of the complexes. All the above process should be taken into account while discussing thermodynamic parameters of complex formation. Meloxicam is bound to β -CD with more negative than the other complexes. Probably geometric factors play a considerable role in the complexation process. It is assumed that the CD cavities size and drugs substituent serve as a steric hindrance for the drug inclusion.

The observed small negative ΔS values for free drugs are assumed to be due to enhancement of disorder in the system. Moreover hydrophobic interactions, which are

long range interactions, can be important in the CDs complex formation. The inclusion complex structures in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 also suggests that benzothiazine ring was partially entrapped in the cavity and interacts with it through hydrophobic interactions. ΔG and ΔH values for the drugs with CDs confirm that all the four inclusion complexes are stable. Comparison of ΔH and ΔS showed that enthalpy changes are higher and entropy changes are lower for the complexation.

The optimized inclusion structures in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 shows formation of hydrogen bond in the inclusion complexes, the intermolecular hydrogen bonds are formed between hydrogen atom of the hydroxy group of the drugs with oxygen atom of primary hydroxy group of the CDs. This shows that both hydrophobic and electrostatic in-

teraction energies are necessary between the drugs and CD to ensure a better inclusion of the drug to the CD. The above values are supported by the fact that the flexibility of the CD molecule may be one of the structural requirements for inclusion complexes formation. The present calculation shows that hydrogen bonding is not responsible for the difference between the binding energies of CD complexation with the drugs.

Table 1 summarizes the HOMO and LUMO energy, chemical potential (μ), stability (S), dipole moment, hardness (η), electrophilicity (ω) and Mulliken charge of the drug (meloxicam and piroxicam), host (α -CD and β -CD) and inclusion complexes. From Table 1, it is found that, (i) chemical potential of piroxicam : α -CD (-5.39 eV) is more negative than other inclusion complexes, (ii) the hardness of meloxicam : CD (4.03 eV) is higher than piroxicam : CD inclusion complexes, (iii) electrophilicity of meloxicam : CD is higher than piroxicam : CD complexes, (iv) the stability of piroxicam : CD complexes are higher than meloxicam : CD complexes, (v) HOMO energy of all the complexes are almost same, (vi) HOMO-LUMO gap for meloxicam : α -CD (-9.11 eV) is more negative than other complexes and (vii) net Mulliken charges for all the inclusion complexes are zero.

Table 1 shows the dipole moment of piroxicam is higher than that of meloxicam. The dipole moments of α -CD and β -CD are higher than those of the respective complexes (meloxicam : α -CD ~ 10.14 D, meloxicam : β -CD ~ 11.06 D, piroxicam : α -CD ~ 11.65 D and piroxicam : β -CD ~ 9.96 D). The dipole moments of the inclusion complexes are higher than the dipole moments for the isolated drug molecules whereas the dipole moment of the inclusion complexes are lower than that of isolated CD molecules (Table 1). This indicates the polarity of the CD cavities decreases after the drug enters the cavities. These values demonstrate a strong relationship with the complexation behavior. Further, the net Mulliken charge distribution analysis reveals that, the values of all the complexes are zero confirming that there are no charge transfer interactions in the CDs complexation. Even though CDs are ready to act as Lewis acid accepting electrons, the guest compounds do not act as Lewis bases donating electrons.

$E_{\text{LUMO}}-E_{\text{HOMO}}$ gap is an important scale of stabi-

lity²⁹ and chemicals with large ($E_{\text{HOMO}}-E_{\text{LUMO}}$) values tend to have higher stability. So, we investigated the electronic structure of the complexes with these considerations using PM3 method. LUMO-HOMO energy gap of meloxicam (-9.04) and piroxicam (-9.01) are shown in Table 1 and Fig. S2, which reveal that the energy gap reflected the chemical activity of the molecules. LUMO as an electron acceptor represents the ability to obtain an electron and HOMO represents the ability to donate electron. Moreover, a lower LUMO-HOMO energy gap explained the eventual stability of the complex, i.e. the isolated molecule had lower stability than the complex molecule.

LUMO-HOMO values of the above four inclusion complexes are varies significantly; i.e. energy gap between LUMO and HOMO of each complex suggests that there will be significant change in the drug molecules driving molecular recognition and binding. This suggests that stability of the inclusion complexes is not equal. The LUMO-HOMO gap for meloxicam : α -CD inclusion complex is more negative suggests that this complex is more stable than the other inclusion complexes. The change in the $E_{\text{LUMO}}-E_{\text{HOMO}}$ gap for the inclusion complexes confirmed the formation of inclusion complexes.

The bond distances, bond angles and the most interesting, dihedral angles, of the drugs before and after complexation in the CD obtained from PM3 calculations for the most stable structure (Fig. 7 and Fig. 8) are presented in Table S2. It is evident that in CDs, the geometry of the drugs are slightly altered. The alterations are significant in dihedral angle, which indicates that these drugs must adopt a specific conformation to form a stable complex. The internal diameter of α -CD is approximately 5.6 Å and β -CD is approximately 6.5 Å. Considering the shape and dimensions of both CDs, both drugs cannot be completely embedded in the CDs nano cavity. The vertical distance and length of the drugs are greater than the upper/lower rim of CDs. Hence, the all rings cannot be fully present inside the CDs nano cavities.

Conclusion

The study of inclusion complexation of meloxicam and piroxicam drugs with α -CD and β -CD, performed by UV-Visible, fluorescence, time resolved fluorescence, and molecular modeling techniques. Increase in fluores-

cence lifetime in CDs solution suggest that both drugs form stable inclusion complexes with CDs. Dual emission noticed in the CD solutions recommended that the energy of the ICT state is lower than that of the locally excited state. The shorter wavelength band was originated from the locally excited state and the longer wavelength band was due to the planar intramolecular charge transfer (PICT) state emission. The ratio of the PICT emission to the normal emission marginally increased with β -CD concentration, while it was slightly increased upon addition of α -CD. The above behavior indicating the formation of different 1 : 1 drug : CD inclusion complexes. The size of the benzamido ring suggested that the orientation of the drug in the β -CD complex is different from that in the α -CD complex. From the computational study, we find that negative complexation energy, Gibbs energy and enthalpy changes for the inclusion complexes indicate that the formation of these complexes is spontaneous, exothermic and hydrogen bonding interactions play a major role in the inclusion process.

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Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <http://dx.doi.org/>.

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